

Virtual brain models: a roadmap towards physiological simulation of neural circuits

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Summary

Virtual Brain Models (VBM) are emerging computational tools promising to revolutionize personalised and precision medicine. VBMs reproduce brain functional dynamics through a generative model that can be constructed and optimized against single subject data, thereby generating what is called a brain digital twin (BDT). VBMs can provide critical information about parameters of network functioning and connectivity but this ability depends on their design, raising some fundamental questions. Can VBM parameters identify key physiological features of the single-subject brain? Are VBM parameters correlated with sensorimotor and cognitive functions? What is still needed to make a VBM more precise in its physiological mechanisms? Simulations in patients affected by neurological diseases are indeed showing that VBMs can operate as effective BDTs capturing essential aspects of the physiopathology of single patients along with relevant physio-psychological correlations. However, the current VBM theory and technology still pose some limitations. We maintain that the evolution of VBM holds the key for a deeper understanding of brain physiology and pathology fostering the development of powerful computational tools capable to support personalized clinical decision making. Here, we will consider a roadmap addressing what VBM and BDT already do well, why this is not enough, what must change, and what becomes possible if it does.

VBM foundations

This section reviews the state of the art of virtual brain models (VBMs) and Brain Digital Twins (BDTs). The rationale for virtual brain modeling addresses fundamental questions at the core of physiology, which deals with causal relationships in complex systems like the brain. Inherent in the VBM theory is the concept of multiscale brain modelling, i.e., the capacity to bridge the microscale to mesoscale and macroscale (D'Angelo & Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, 2017; D'Angelo & Jirsa, 2022; Deco et al., 2008; Einevoll et al., 2019). This holds the promise to explain several fundamental physiological phenomena linking the activity of membrane molecules (e.g., ionic channels and receptors) to that of neurons and networks up to the whole brain. However, the full implementation of this approach is still incomplete.

The theory and technology of VBMs have been reported in detail (Deco et al., 2008; Jirsa et al., 2010; Schirner et al., 2018)(Hashemi et al., 2025)(Ghosh et al., 2008). In VBM, the brain is seen as a collection of active areas connected by fibre tracts, where the connectivity is explicitly split into short-range intracortical and long-range corticocortical (connectomic) fiber systems, each with its own propagation delay. Together with local grey matter node dynamics, this architecture is formally captured in the Jirsa–Haken equation (V. K. Jirsa & Haken, 1996, 1997). Therefore, the construction of a VBM is the result of three operations: the structural white matter connectome reconstruction (weights and time delays), grey matter node description through neural population models, and model parameter tuning through optimization or inference. VBM, by leveraging brain structure and function, can generate large-scale network dynamics, which are the closest proxy of brain activity. It would therefore be desirable that VBMs are as close as possible to anatomy and physiology, making them research tools capable of identifying the underpinnings of certain physiological functions and pathologies (Wang et al., 2024).

Connectome reconstruction and node description

VBM starts with a regional reconstruction of the brain through a subdivision in areas connected by fiber bundles, which, in their ensemble, form the structural connectome. This reconstruction is based on MRI technologies that include high resolution structural scans and advanced water diffusion-weighted sequences. In addition, functional recordings are essential for the actual VBM tuning (see next section) and currently rely on resting-state blood oxygenation level dependent (BOLD) weighted sequences. The nodes are identified based on anatomical or functional parcellation of the brain's grey matter regions and contain models generating local neural dynamics, e.g., using neural mass models, mean field models, or spiking neural networks (Fig. 1). What makes these virtual brains functional are therefore the local node dynamics that propagate to other nodes through the connectome, generating large-scale oscillations mimicking those of electroencephalogram (EEG) or fMRI recordings. Cellular properties can be propagated into the VBM following a workflow passing through different levels of simplification and abstraction (Fig. 2). Interestingly, since the connectome can be extracted from MRI tractography in single subjects, the model can be personalized, setting the basis for the first level of personalization of VBMs. Independent from node description, VBM uses a global coupling parameter, G , that represents the connectivity strength between nodes. As a first assumption, this parameter is unique for the network under consideration (or the whole brain), while the relative importance of a connection is reported by the corresponding tract property (currently the tract density d) provided by the structural connectivity matrix. The nodes, in turn, contain parameters describing local network properties. For example, the Wong-Wang model (Wong & Wang, 2006) proves particularly useful because it allows to extract parameters of physiological relevance comprising excitatory coupling (J_{NMDA}), inhibitory coupling (J_{GABA}), and recurrent excitation (J_{rec}) of an inhibitory and excitatory neural populations. These parameters are related to neurotransmission mechanisms involving NMDA and GABA-A receptors. As a whole, the model yields information about the

excitation/inhibition (E/I) balance in the nodes, e.g., calculated as $E/I = (J_{\text{NMDA}} + J_{\text{rec}}) / J_{\text{GABA}}$ (Deco et al., 2014; Li et al., 2025).

Parameter tuning through optimization and parameter extraction

Once the VBM has been reconstructed, it must be optimized to the individual brain through a second level of personalization, that is parameter tuning. This step instantiates model inversion: the recovery of generative-model parameters from macroscale measurements (Jirsa et al., 2002; Roy & Jirsa, 2013; Spiegler & Jirsa, 2013). Because the same macroscopic activity can be produced by many distinct microscopic configurations, the inverse problem is fundamentally degenerate (Edelman & Gally, 2001; Tononi et al., 1999), and the solution must remain at the mesoscopic scale (Lorenzi et al., 2025; Sacha et al., 2025; Zerlaut et al., 2017, 2018). Inversion is performed against data features of within-subject recordings such as the static functional connectivity matrix, dynamic functional connectivity, and regional power spectra. The choice of data features strongly constrains what can be recovered, an issue we revisit below when discussing the physiology of VBMs.

Two methodological families address the inversion problem and should be clearly distinguished. The first reduces it to optimization: a discrepancy between simulated and empirical features. A popular choice is the Pearson correlation of the FC matrix combined with the Kolmogorov–Smirnov distance over the FCD histogram, e.g. $\text{cost} = \min(\text{PCC} + (1 - \text{KSD}))$ (Deco et al., 2011, 2017; Demirtaş et al., 2016). This metric is minimized by gradient descent or evolutionary algorithms (Li et al., 2025), yielding a single best-fitting parameter vector. The second approach is more elaborate and computes the posterior distribution $p(\theta|y)$; it therefore returns the full landscape of plausible configurations consistent with the data, and not just a single parameter vector. Within this Bayesian family, several options coexist: variational and Laplace approximations such as Dynamic Causal Modelling, which constrain the posterior to a tractable parametric form (Friston et al., 2019; Zeidman et al., 2023); Markov chain Monte Carlo schemes that sample the posterior directly (Hashemi et al., 2020, 2021); and simulation-based inference, in which neural density estimators are trained on prior-predictive simulations and subsequently produce a posterior for any new subject in a matter of seconds, without retraining (Hashemi et al., 2023; Ziaemehr et al., 2025). The practical distinction is not which family is intrinsically more accurate, but what kind of object the inversion delivers (whether this is a single point, a parametric envelope, a sample cloud, or an amortized density) since this object determines the kind of physiological claim that can subsequently be supported quantitatively (Hashemi et al., 2025).

The output of inversion is a personalized parameterization of the generative model which, together with the connectome, constitutes the BDT. In current practice only the parameters tied to the intended use case are inferred — for instance regional excitabilities for the epileptogenic-zone problem, or conduction velocities for multiple sclerosis — while the remaining parameters are constrained from the literature. This restriction supports identifiability and convergence. Tuning can be applied to the whole brain or to predefined networks (resting-state networks, task-engaged networks); beyond the global coupling G , the inferred parameters depend on the node model in use, e.g., J_{NMDA} , J_{GABA} , and J_{rec} for Wong–Wang nodes (Wong & Wang, 2006).

VBM identifies physiopathological features of patient’s brain

This section addresses the conceptual diagnosis and the inherent validation operated through VBMs and BDTs at the current state. A key step is to demonstrate the ability of VBMs to capture salient alterations of

brain properties linked to the brain functional dynamics, previously reported in patients using different techniques, for example neurophysiological recordings and postmortem histological assessments. But the grand challenge is to capture the variance of subject-level neurological and neuropsychological deficits through VBM parameters in vivo (Fig. 3). Importantly, VBMs can capture alterations in large-scale networks including multiple brain regions up to the whole brain. Typically, VBM is used to simulate resting-state networks including the default mode network (DMN), the attention and salience networks (VAN and DAN), the limbic network (LN), the frontoparietal network (FPN), the somatomotor network (SMN), the basal-ganglia network (BGN), and various sensory networks.

Dementia

Pathologies in the dementia spectrum - including Alzheimer disease (AD) and frontotemporal dementia (FTD) - are characterized by specific alterations of thalamocortical circuits. A critical BDT validation is thus to capture AD and FTD signatures in groups of patients. Indeed, VBM revealed a pattern of changes matching what is known from physiopathological and anatomopathological analysis: there was increased G and E/I balance in the default mode network (DMN) in both AD and FTD patients, but there was reduced G and E/I balance in the Fronto-parietal network (FPN) in FTD patients only (Monteverdi et al., 2022, 2023, 2025). The G increase of the DMN is consistent with the known hyper-synchrony of this network. The E/I balance was calculated from the Wong-Wang neural mass model and could be broken down into specific parameter changes more specifically. The NMDA receptor function (J_{NMDA}) was reduced in the DMN of AD compatible with memory loss, while the GABA receptor function (J_{GABA}) was reduced in the FPN of FTD compatible with prefrontal disinhibition. Therefore, BDTs can distinguish AD from FTD patients based on their inherent network properties. However, in the prodromic phase of dementia called Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), in which neural circuit alterations are limited and heterogeneous, no significant differences in BDT parameters could be observed compared to healthy controls. This is possibly a reflection of the coarse nature of the current construction of neural mass models.

The BDT analysis was then brought forward to capture single subject variability. Both in MCI, AD, and FTD, VBM parameters showed high correlation with neuropsychological scores over multiple cognitive domains relevant to the pathology (Zimmermann et al., 2018) (Monteverdi et al., 2022, 2023, 2025). These physiopsychological correlations reveal high sensitivity of VBM for single subjects also in MCI and not just in more severe AD and FTD cases. The NMDA and GABA receptor-mediated transmission impairment was quantitatively correlated with the learning and memory ability of subjects explaining E/I balance alterations (Li et al., 2025). Interestingly, BDT parameters can be linked to molecular pathways (Stefanovski et al., 2019) to augment machine-learning-based classification of dementia (Triebkorn et al., 2022).

Parkinson disease and cerebellar ataxias

Parkinson's disease and ataxias are characterized by prominent alterations of the basal ganglia and cerebellum properties, respectively. In both cases, the coexistence of cognitive-affective symptoms suggests the involvement of multiple resting-state networks.

Parkinson's disease is a neurological condition characterized by motor, cognitive and neurovegetative symptoms determined by a reduced Dopamine production in the substantia nigra. BDT models integrate EEG, deep-brain electrode recordings, and structural-functional connectivity to simulate how dopamine levels shape whole-brain dynamics. Such models can accurately infer an individual patient's dopaminergic state before and after L-DOPA administration, validating the approach against real electrophysiological data (Angiolelli et al., 2025a). Moreover, multiscale cosimulations of a spiking basal ganglia model in a BDTs may

open the door to predict the impact of deep brain stimulation on large-scale brain dynamics in Parkinsonian patients (Meier et al., 2022).

Cerebellar ataxias are rare heterogeneous disorders marked by motor incoordination and cognitive–affective deficits that can be distinguished between congenital forms, such as Joubert syndrome (JS), and slowly progressive (SP) ataxias. BDTs revealed that both groups have reduced volume and structural connectivity in the SMN and VAN but with different topological and dynamical signatures: SP showed reduced centrality and impaired excitation–inhibition balance in SMN, while JS showed VAN alterations accompanied by compensatory increases in functional core nodes and excitatory coupling. Overall, DBTs showed that cerebellar damage disrupts large-scale networks in both conditions, but only JS reveal compensatory reorganisation. Importantly, network parameters correlated with motor and cognitive performance accounting for individual clinical profiles, supporting precise patient stratification toward personalised therapies (Gaviraghi et al., 2026).

Multiple sclerosis

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a neuroinflammatory disease compromising axonal myelination and signal communication between brain regions. Personalised whole-brain BDTs integrating structural connectivity and electrophysiological data have been used to estimate conduction delays, which have emerged as stronger predictors of disability than traditional markers of structural damage (Sorrentino et al., 2024)(Mazzara et al., 2025). It would be useful to understand how BDT technology can complement statistical learning models of the onset and progression of MS-related brain atrophy to predict each patient’s structural trajectory (Cen et al., 2023). Together, these developments point toward a future in which personalised digital replicas of MS patients help identify early disease onset, stratify progression patterns, and guide more precise therapeutic strategies

Epilepsy

Epilepsies originate from paroxysmal hyperexcitability of brain regions most located into the cerebral cortex and can be determined by a multitude of causes altering the local E/I balance. Recent developments in BDTs and VBM are transforming the study and treatment of pharmaco-resistant epilepsy, offering new ways to identify epileptogenic networks and personalise interventions. Virtual brain twins integrating functional recordings such as EEG and stereo-EEG can simulate seizure dynamics at the whole-brain level. This approach has been validated on large cohorts and is currently being tested in clinical trials to improve localisation of the epileptogenic zone (Wang et al., 2025). By modelling how seizures are triggered through invasive stereotactic EEG (SEEG) stimulation or emerging non-invasive methods such as temporal interference (Missey et al., 2026), researchers can estimate the epileptogenic zone network with greater precision and potentially reduce the need for invasive procedures. These models reproduce how seizures start and spread using mechanistic neural mass models like the Epileptor (Houssaini et al., 2020), enabling clinicians to test different stimulation strategies *in silico* before applying them to the patient. More broadly, personalised whole-brain models are becoming a recognised tool for presurgical evaluation, helping clinicians simulate seizure propagation, assess surgical targets, and anticipate functional consequences. As evidence grows for their predictive power, virtual brain twins are expected to support more accurate diagnosis, guide treatment decisions, and ultimately offer non-invasive alternatives for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy (V. Jirsa et al., 2023).

Wrap-up: what are BDTs telling us about the pathological brain

This remarkable set of examples is revealing the ability of BDTs to address the multifaceted nature of brain pathology, capturing neuronal functional properties otherwise hidden in large scale signal recordings. First,

BDTs can be used to address pathophysiological questions in neurodegeneration (as in dementia, Parkinson disease, ataxias), neuroinflammation (multiple sclerosis), and hyperexcitability (epilepsies), summarizing three main categories of brain dysfunctional mechanisms. Secondly, BDTs can deal with alterations in the major brain circuits, including the thalamocortical system, cerebellum, hippocampus, and basal ganglia, that eventually control sensorimotor and cognitive affective behaviour (D'Angelo, 2019). Thirdly, combined with other metrics derived from graph theory and EEG, BDTs can distinguish primary damage from compensatory reorganization. Lastly, the key difference between large scale properties of the brain, captured through quantitative MRI of the brain and BDTs is that BDTs can address different patho-genetic mechanisms, including genetic and epigenetic alterations in neuronal membrane excitability, axonal conduction, synaptic transmission, and neuromodulation, linking pathology and behaviour to neuronal function.

These results bear an important physiological message: high-level brain dynamics can be captured by a model based on structural connectivity and intrinsic oscillators. And show that the VBM is flexible enough to accommodate different pathological changes that eventually reflect into parameters and terms of the master equation of the model (Wang et al., 2024). This way, VBMs generate the basis for effective BDTs. BDT parameter integration into machine-learning classification algorithms eventually allow to generate effective *virtual patients* of multiple brain diseases.

VBM assumptions: beyond current limitations

This section addresses key limitations of current VBT and BDT implementations proposing solutions to advance beyond the current state of the art. To do so, we need to address in more depth how VBM operates. We therefore will consider a set of underlying assumptions about the nodes and their connections that resemble symmetry, homogeneity, and isotropy in physics (Mainzer, 2013). Given the complexity of the brain, these simplifications are acceptable to begin with, currently allowing to manage virtual brain modelling and simulation and providing relevant insights into brain organization and function (Deco et al., 2011, 2013, 2017). The surprising capacity of VBMs in capturing network properties in pathologies is a proof that these assumptions hold on the large scale, but they also pose limitations that need to be relaxed (Fousek et al., 2022; Sacha et al., 2025; Ziaemehr et al., 2025) to make VBMs closer to brain anatomy and physiology and to broaden their applicability. As a drawback, increasing biological mimetic, while improving the physiological meaning of VBM, broadens the parameter space leading to some theoretical and technical issues that are considered below.

Symmetry of the brain connectivity

The MRI connectome is taken as a good proxy of brain structural connectivity, but there are some caveats. (1) In MRI tractography there are no axons but fibre tracts. While tracts are on the same spatial scale of the node-based representation used in the virtual brain, which does not consider neuron and axons but only populations of excitable elements, fine grain details about neural communication are lost. (2) Synaptic relays cannot be detected by MRI tractography, so unless imposed as a stopping point, they are ignored. Moreover, the MRI tracts do not contain information about the versus and sign (i.e. inhibition or excitation) of signal transmission. (3) MRI tracts, due to reconstruction issues, may contain false negative and false positives and therefore need curation. (4) Short-range connections between closely spaced regions (e.g., the basal ganglia circuits, intra-cortical or intra-cerebellar circuits, brainstem circuits) are usually under resolved, but with highly dense tracts between their identified grey matter parcellations.

One main consequence of deriving the connectome from MRI tractography is that is symmetric with an impac that was quantified systematically (Melozzi et al., 2017). At present, the structural connectivity

matrix of the network N derived from MRI tractography is $\mathbf{M}^d = \mathbf{d}(N)$, and it is intrinsically symmetric and positive, while brain connectivity is not. For example, connections between the cerebellar cortex and deep cerebellar nuclei are inhibitory and unidirectional, as it is the case for several connections between basal ganglia nuclei. Connectivity should be rather seen as a product of matrices including sign and directionality, $\mathbf{M}^{dir} \times \mathbf{M}^{sign}$. Therefore, a big effort should be devoted to curate the MRI connectome beforehand and introduce this information as a prior (Fig. 4).

Homogeneity of nodes

All nodes are currently represented using the same type of model, e.g., a Wong-Wang (Wong & Wang, 2006) or Jansen-Rit (Jansen & Rit, 1995) or Epileptor (Houssaini et al., 2020) neural mass. But this homogeneity is not the case in nature, since local microcircuits are the most diverse depending on the brain region (e.g., cortical microcolumns feature a radically different architecture and functional organization compared to cerebellar cortical modules and are not a feature of deep grey matter structures). Moreover, node representations are oversimplified, since neural masses usually consist of just two elements, one excitatory and the other inhibitory, which are reciprocally and recurrently connected. And these two elements sum up the properties of the multitude of different neuron types along with their specific and diversified neuronal interactions. The neural mass representation captures essential dynamical properties common to most brain circuits, including the E/I balance, recurrent excitation, and oscillations. However, they miss the diversity, algorithmic ability and distributed parallelized processing properties of local microcircuits. Therefore, an effort is needed to improve the diversity of nodes and their computational capabilities, e.g. exploiting algorithmic representations called mean field models (see Fig. 2).

Globality of parameters

In the optimization process, parameters are often considered global rather than local variables. While this restricts the parameter space and improves the computational efficiency during model optimization, using global parameters prevents the independent tuning that would be needed to generate a physiologically meaningful circuit. The most important parameters to consider are inter-node communication (global network coupling), communication speeds, and intra-node synaptic strength.

Network coupling

In the current VBM layout, G represents global coupling for the whole brain or for a specific brain circuit and the relative importance of a connection is reported by the corresponding tract density, d , provided by the structural connectivity matrix. However, local connections between nodes need to be set independently and should keep into consideration synaptic efficacy, e , i.e., the capacity of a given tract to transmit (which is relatively independent from its size). In other words, a tract may be large but transmit a little amount of information, or *vice versa*. Thus, in general, in the network N , communication between two nodes, $A \rightarrow B$, will initially depend on $d(A \rightarrow B)$ but then this matrix can be substituted by $e(A \rightarrow B)$. This process can be extended to all nodes in N generating the matrix $\mathbf{M}^e = \mathbf{e}(N)$. In summary, d is known since it is given by MRI tractography, while e is a free model parameter. In principle, \mathbf{M}^d could be used as a seed for model initialization but should eventually be substituted by \mathbf{M}^e , which in turn can be extracted through model optimization (see Fig. 4).

Communication delays

Another critical issue is the speed of internode communication, which causes delays impacting on brain dynamics. The motion equation describing the problem is simply $\Delta \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{s}/\mathbf{v}$, where $\Delta \mathbf{t}$ is the matrix of transmission delays, \mathbf{s} is the matrix of internodal distances, and \mathbf{v} is the matrix of conduction velocities. Now the conduction speed is considered constant for all tracts (i.e., \mathbf{v} has the same value everywhere) but

this is not what happens in the brain (e.g., big axons are faster than small axons and myelinated axons are faster than unmyelinated axons). Moreover, the tract length is often measured as the Euclidean distance between nodes, rather than the actual tract length. Therefore, delays need to be recalculated, as they critically impact on node synchrony and therefore on the simulated functional connectivity matrix, with a detrimental effect on global dynamics (a critical case occurs in pathologies like multiple sclerosis, see (Sorrentino et al., 2024)). The coupling of VBMs has a space-time structure of connectivity (Petkoski & Jirsa, 2019, 2022), which is spanned by the tensor of connection weights and time delays. This in turn affects the optimization process and the *cost* function impacting model quality. E.g., suppose that the distance is double and the speed is half the global value, so that for a given tract $A \rightarrow B$, $\Delta t = s/v$ will quadruplicate. On the $A \rightarrow B$ tract originally calibrated to be 0.1 m and conducting at 10 m/sec, Δt would change from 100 ms to 400 ms, which is enough to generate a considerable error in nodal communication and network synchronization. Therefore, s and v should be given *a priori* from independent estimates of tract length and conduction velocity.

Intra-node synaptic strength

When local node parameters are extracted by VBM optimization (e.g. excitatory or inhibitory strengths), they are usually kept the same in all the nodes of a specific network or of the whole brain. But this is not the case for the natural brain. Consider, e.g., a somatomotor network including the cerebellum, the thalamus, and the cerebral cortex, which are now represented by identical Wong-Wang neural masses. The NMDA and GABA-A receptor-dependent strengths are present both in the cerebellar, in the cerebro-cortical, and in the thalamic circuit, but the neural mechanisms and network organization are quite different. Moreover, there is no recurrent excitation in the cerebellar nodes, but this mechanism is remarkable in the neocortical nodes. In the thalamus, instead, excitation and inhibition are segregated in different nuclei coupled in closed-loop with the cerebral cortex. Nonetheless, the parameters representing NMDA and GABA-A receptor-dependent strength are forced to be the same all over the network. Clearly, a different approach is needed, which differentiates the networks and their parameters in agreement with the biological nature of the circuits. Mathematically, the problem changes from a unique parameter set $P(N) = P_k(N)$ to the parameter matrix $\mathbf{P}(N) = P_{i,j}(n_i)$, where $n_i \in N$ are network nodes, $P_{i,j}$ are the j parameters of node i , and $j > k$. Clearly, $\mathbf{P}_{i,j}(n_i) \gg P_k(N)$. Therefore, new technologies are needed to reliably estimate and subsequently tune these many parameters.

What is the solution?

Breaking the symmetry of the network, the homogeneity of nodes, and the globality of parameters (Fousek et al., 2022; Sacha et al., 2025) implies to consider the three equations below:

- 1) Internode communication: $\mathbf{M}^* = \mathbf{M}^{dir} \times \mathbf{M}^{sign} \times \mathbf{M}^e$
- 2) Internode delay: $\Delta t = s/v$
- 3) Node parameters: $\mathbf{P}(N) = P_{i,j}(n_i)$

This approach implies an increase of the parameter space along with the ability to impose additional priors for \mathbf{M}^{dir} , \mathbf{M}^{sign} , and Δt , and to extract parameter values for \mathbf{M}^e and $\mathbf{P}(N)$.

Introducing more information a priori in the generative model

To parameterize an expanded set of free parameters avoiding overfitting, more structural and functional constraints are needed. That the VBM in the current formulation does not allow to extract all the information contained in MRI data was demonstrated by combining information about the relative importance of nodes in a network using graph theory (GT) with VBM parameters. In resting state networks,

GT parameters addressing the relationship between nodes augmented the ability of VBM parameters in explaining neuropsychological scores over multiple cognitive and sensorimotor domains (Monteverdi et al., 2025). This indicates that $d(N)$ is not sufficient and that integrating GT information, e.g., in $e(N)$, should improve VBM by personalizing inter-node communication. A similar result is being achieved using the power spectral density of source EEG signals in the same regions segmented for VBM (Monteverdi et al., 2026). In this case, the EEG information could be integrated to constrain the oscillatory bands of nodal activity (Lorenzi et al., 2025). Other recording techniques may be used to obtain further *a priori* information about model parameters, e.g., DCM for node communication, MRI spectroscopy for the E/I balance, NIRS for blood flow, FDG-PET for local node metabolism. The corresponding information should eventually be embedded in equations 1-3. Specific MRI techniques have been recently proposed to estimate the conduction delays, Δt as shown in preliminary work by Lupi et al ISMRM 2025-2026.

Generating region-specific mean field models

To differentiate brain circuits and embed as much biological information as possible, specific circuit models are needed. Given the limit of the inversion problem determined by degeneracy (Edelman & Gally, 2001; Tononi et al., 1999), the solution should stay on the mesoscale, which is compatible with the tractographic representation of brain connectivity and a probabilistic mass description of neural activity. The technology that matches this requirement is the mean-field model (MFM) (Sacha et al., 2025; Zerlaut et al., 2018), which is generated bottom-up transferring biological knowledge into the node (Lorenzi et al., 2025). The MFM can maintain the distinction between different neuronal populations and their synaptic connectivity. The MFM elaborates an I/O function in terms of mean and variance of realistic population firing rates instead of representing generic oscillatory activities. Examples of region-specific MFMs have been provided for the cerebellum, the neocortex, and hippocampus CA1 (Goldman et al., 2020; Lorenzi et al., 2023; Tesler et al., 2024).

It has already been proved that MFMs can effectively operate into a VBM improving its performance and resolving some of the issue reported above (Lorenzi et al., 2023, 2025). The cerebellar MFM can resolve the inadequacy of generic neural masses in representing the cerebellar circuit. It is made of all the 4 main neuronal populations of the cerebellar cortex, including the granule cells, Golgi cells, Purkinje cells, and molecular layer interneurons, and resolves well the cerebellar cortex activity under different functional conditions. The MFM can oscillate on specific bands determined by the neural mechanisms of the embedded spiking neural network. Moreover, several cerebellar MFMs have been interconnected implementing the mesoscale connectivity of multiple cerebellar nodes with deep cerebellar nuclei, that is not properly resolved by MRI tractography. Finally, the fMRI signal was related to the specific neuronal population that is most involved in generating it, the granule cells, improving the matching between simulated and empirical functional connectivity matrices (Lorenzi et al., 2023, 2025).

Curating the connectome

Connectome curation can be distinguished between macro-, meso- and micro-scale. While meso- and micro-scale connections are probably better resolved by engineering the MFMs (e.g., see (Lorenzi et al., 2025)), long-range connectivity requires curation to eliminate false positives and to give directionality and sign to fibre tracts. This means accessing anatomical and physiological information and use it for the curation process, creating masks that can be superimposed to the MRI structural connectivity matrix of single subjects. Some corrections can be performed directly using appropriate anatomical and physiological data reported in literature. For example, the cerebello-thalamo-cortico-ponto-cerebellar loop has been manually curated to eliminate spurious homolateral tracts and introduce anterior pontine nuclei not resolved by atlas-based segmentation, improving model optimization (Palesi et al., 2020). Another way

could be to use an atlas constructed *ad hoc* to explore specific networks or functional tasks (Gaviraghi et al., 2025). This strategy could ensure high precision but may be impractical to be extended to the whole brain, for which the creation of an *ad hoc* atlas is most needed.

Estimating multiple model parameters

Accurately estimating parameters in whole-brain models remains a major challenge due to the high dimensionality and nonlinear dynamics of these systems. This problem is typically addressed through either traditional optimization approaches or Bayesian inference frameworks. Traditional optimization methods identify single optimal parameter values by minimizing discrepancy metrics, like the cost function explained above, but they generally produce point estimates that do not capture parameter uncertainty or the global structure of the objective landscape. Evolutionary approaches, such as genetic algorithms, have also been successfully applied to parameterize virtual brain models (Li et al., 2025). In contrast, Bayesian frameworks—including Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC), maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimation, and variational Bayesian inference—aim to infer full posterior distributions over parameters, thereby quantifying uncertainty. More recently, Simulation-Based Inference has gained increasing attention for complex models with intractable likelihood functions. By leveraging amortized learning, SBI enables rapid and personalized parameter inference while avoiding many of the convergence issues associated with traditional sampling-based approaches. Likelihood-free approaches such as Virtual Bayesian Inference provide a promising framework for model inversion when only a prior distribution, a simulator, and observed data are available (Ziaemehr et al., 2025).

Scaling inversion to whole-brain models, with regional excitabilities, multiple coupling parameters and node-specific dynamics estimated jointly, brings up three concerns. First, the choice of inversion procedure is not a tuning detail but determines what the result can support: a point estimate from cost-function minimization or genetic algorithms (Li et al., 2025) cannot quantify uncertainty or expose degenerate parameter directions, even when its fit is excellent. Second, the geometry of the configuration space matters: posteriors for these models are typically anisotropic and curved, parameters are often correlated, and sampler convergence frequently requires reparameterization, hierarchical structure or non-centered formulations (Hashemi et al., 2020, 2024). Third, model selection should be performed on model evidence rather than on a single goodness-of-fit statistic; this is what WAIC, PSIS-LOO and free energy under the Laplace approximation provide, leveraging the full posterior to estimate out-of-sample predictive accuracy at minimal additional cost (Vehtari et al., 2017; Hashemi et al., 2021). For these reasons, simulation-based inference is one of the most promising of these schemes for clinical translation, as the remaining bottleneck is no longer sampling efficiency but the design of the low-dimensional features that summarize the empirical data, which, as we argue below, is also at the root of how VBMs are currently evaluated.

Wrap-up: a priori knowledge, parameter inference, and degeneracy

It is now worth summarizing which parameters are priors (i.e., given or fixed a priori) and what are inferred using the VBM. In state-of-the-art BDTs, the communication between nodes is parameterized using the tract density $\mathbf{d}(N)$ obtained from MRI tractography. The posterior parameters are global coupling, a scaling factor G applied to the whole network, and local coupling parameters that depend on the node model (e.g., J_{NMDA} , J_{GABA} , J_{rec} in the Wong-Wang model). In future VBT models, the prior and posteriors will change providing additional and more detailed information about brain networks by leveraging advanced connectome and nodal representations through multiparametric optimization algorithms. The tract density $\mathbf{d}(N)$ (prior) will be used as a seed but then the specific node-to-node weights will be inferred, together with G , to yield the effective connectivity $\mathbf{e}(N)$ (posterior). Local coupling parameters will correspond to extended set of communication weights in mean-field model (e.g., for the cerebellar network, weight for

communication between granule cells, Golgi cells, Purkinje cells, and molecular layer interneurons). This evolution implies that more information is extracted from the data and the precision of the models could be further augmented by using multimodal recordings to constrain the generative model (e.g., not only MRI but also EEG, MEG etc). By increasing information extraction from the data, degeneracy will be reduced (but not fully eliminated though) improving the physiological understanding of brain network functioning.

The physiology of virtual brain models

To paraphrase Rodolfo Llinas, *“most neuroscientists feel that two orders of magnitude above and below one’s central focus is «horizon enough», and that anyone attempting four orders above and below is reckless. However, there are some who attempt such a dangerous dynamic range. They probably know that the risk of failure is the price of synthesis, without which there are only fields of dismembered parts”* (Llinás, 2002). The architectural ambition Llinás describes is precisely the one VBM were built to support with the aim of capturing essential aspects of the physiology of the multiscale brain.

But the question poses itself on what are the physiological implications of VBMs and why do they work so well despite all the simplifications? The model inversion process yields estimate of parameters governing signal communication between and within nodes. In specific cases, the E/I balance can be decomposed into receptor-specific transmission strengths at glutamatergic and GABAergic synapses (Wong & Wang, 2006) (Li et al., 2025). Information can be obtained for any identified resting-state network, and combined with topological and electrophysiological data, VBM parameters can support the identification of dysfunctional and compensatory processes in circuits otherwise not accessible in humans in vivo. Finally, these parameters correlate with neuropsychological and sensorimotor performance. VBMs thus appear to provide information about latent microscopic variables by observing macroscale phenomena, as anticipated by model design (D’Angelo & Jirsa, 2022).

Strikingly, this works even though the molecular and cellular determinants of brain function are far from fully resolved: large-scale brain dynamics are captured by models built on structural connectivity, intrinsic oscillators and often strikingly harsh simplifications of the space-time structure of inter-areal communication (Cayco-Gajic et al., 2017; Deco et al., 2008, 2011, 2013, 2014, 2017, 2021; Schirner et al., 2018, 2023)(Petkoski & Jirsa, 2019, 2022). At the same time, current VBMs operate well in resting state but not yet on task-dependent simulations, can only marginally perform effective computations, and do not express adaptation or awareness — they are still missing essential mechanisms and architectures that subtend brain functioning, preventing them from behaving as biological systems characterized by adaptability, intelligence and consciousness (Koch, 2004). Looking downwards toward the microscale, VBMs do not yet incorporate dendritic processing, spike timing or synaptic plasticity. Looking upwards toward the macroscale, they lack the oriented and specific connectivity subtending sensorimotor and cognitive functions and are not yet connected to sensory systems or a body, remaining “locked-in” without feedback or feedforward connections to the world; they are also deprived of learning capabilities and cannot change their functional state as real brains do.

This architectural framing motivates a more critical epistemological analysis of the current state of VBMs. We organize it around three questions: how simulations should be evaluated against data, where the missing physiology actually lays, and how to interpret the apparent paradox that simplified coarse-grained models capture macroscale dynamics at all. These three concerns bear directly on what BDT findings can and cannot license clinically.

One consideration is certainly the evaluation-metric question. The dominant practice in the field evaluates simulated activity against empirical recordings using the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) of the static functional connectivity matrix, sometimes augmented by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov distance (KSD) of the dynamic functional connectivity histogram, combined into ad hoc composite criteria such as $\text{cost} = \min(\text{PCC} + (1 - \text{KSD}))$ (Deco et al., 2011, 2017; Demirtaş et al., 2016). The metric choice has well known and consequential weaknesses. Static FC is a second-order summary of an explicitly non-stationary process and a single scalar PCC over a parcellated FC matrix discards phase and frequency content. PCC is also invariant to affine rescaling, so models that systematically over- or under-estimate coupling are not penalized by the metric. Furthermore, the empirical FC against which simulations are evaluated is itself an estimator of limited reliability. At typical scan durations the test-retest reliability is modest, and the 70-pipeline meta-analysis on a single shared dataset (Botvinik-Nezer et al., 2020) demonstrated that pipeline choices alone produce sizeable variation in the resulting FC. Most importantly, goodness-of-fit on FC is not the same as goodness-of-inference on parameters: degeneracy makes it possible to reach low cost on extended manifolds in parameter space, so that the recovered values of G , J_{NMDA} , J_{GABA} , and so on may reflect the projection of the inversion onto an arbitrary axis of that manifold rather than physiology. In this light, the impressive correlations between BDT parameters and neuropsychological scores warrant interpretive caution: when uncertainty is not quantified and model comparison is not performed, so that the strength of a correlation does not establish the identifiability of the parameter that produces it.

As a consequence, a more principled evaluation strategy has been articulated within the BDT framework itself (Hashemi et al., 2025) and should be adopted as the field matures: posterior predictive checks across multiple, complementary data features — static FC, FCD distributions, regional power spectral densities, neuronal cascade statistics, edge time series, metastability indices — combined with out-of-sample validation and model comparison via marginal-likelihood-based criteria. The point is not that PCC of FC is uninformative; it is that it is one statistic among many, and its dominance in the field has been a matter of historical convenience rather than methodological deliberation.

Another consideration is the missing physiological detail and oversimplifications. There is a conventional list of physiological gaps such as dendritic processing, spike timing, plasticity at the microscale; body, sensorium, and learning at the macroscale. Then there is a clear under-exploitation of existing physiological dimensions that are already inside the framework. Foremost among them are the time delays of the connectome. The Jirsa-Haken equation has accommodated heterogeneous conduction delays since 1996 and the multiple sclerosis studies have demonstrated that conduction delays are stronger predictors of clinical disability than lesion load (Mazzara et al., 2025; Sorrentino et al., 2024). Petkoski and Jirsa (Petkoski & Jirsa, 2019, 2022) have shown that the joint space-time structure of connectivity spanned by weights and time delays produces a frequency-specific normalization of the connectome that explains the emergence of resting-state spectral cores: visual at alpha, default mode at beta, sensorimotor and auditory at gamma. The widespread use of Hopf-type oscillator networks coupled through structural connectivity but without explicit time delays (Deco et al., 2017; Deco & Kringelbach, 2020) is therefore a strong simplification that erases the resonance structure responsible for frequency-band specificity. A more balanced approach should estimate the validation sensitivity of missing physiological details and assumed simplifications of existing architectural features. Likely time delays are not a numerical nuisance to be absorbed into a global scaling, but are physiology, and they should be inferred (as in the MS work) and curated.

Thus, as explained above, the introduction of a curated directional connectome including direct estimates of conduction velocities and of mean-field models propagating elementary properties to higher scales

maintaining the resonance structure of local microcircuits, will prove critical for the physiological and pathophysiological interpretation of VBT parameters.

Toward brain digital twins for clinical and technological applications

At this point let us speculate about a plausible future with a horizon of 5-10 years moving from the first to second generation of VBMs with enhanced potential for physiological interpretability, clinical translation, and technological application. While VBMs can now faithfully reproduce brain waves in resting state, they may considerably improve with the solution of eq.1-3. These, by incorporating mean-field models, curated connectome, and conduction velocities (figs 3 and 4), would allow a more reliable simulation of physiological mechanisms and the interpretation of pathological changes while addressing details of network alterations. The mean field models contain diverse neuron types connected according to anatomical and physiological data and are parameterized accurately toward the corresponding spiking neural networks. Therefore, mean field models can transfer biological details and specific local network dynamics into the VBM, along with precise representations of pathological alterations at the molecular and cellular level (Lorenzi et al., 2025) (Fig. 3). Studies are indeed already ongoing to understand how much cellular and subcellular properties brought into the mean fields emerge at the macroscale. The curated and signed connectome imports the orientation and sign of interregional communication into the VBM and can therefore allow to identify organized communication pathways laying the basis of brain functioning (Arbib et al., 1997)(Singer, 2009) (Thivierge & Marcus, 2007). This second generation of VBMs will open the way to analyze the physiology of the self-organizing nervous system in conditions like stimulus-response tasks, cognitive tasks, or learning tasks broadening the applicability to medicine and technology.

While second generation VBMs are advancing, a third wave of changes is under development. The direct incorporation of spiking models is now being explored both on the reduced scale of a virtual mouse brain (Melozzi et al., 2017) (Geminiani et al., 2026) and in the human VBM (Tartarini et al., 2026) (Meier et al., 2022). The first attempts at implementing neuromodulator systems are appearing to allow VBMs to dynamically regulate brains states (Angiolelli et al., 2025b; Martin et al., 2025). And neurobots incorporating spiking neural networks and synaptic learning rules are showing that closed loop control of the body-environment interaction could change the game, implementing autonomous learning, sensory prediction, and adaptation (D'Angelo et al., 2025). The expansion of robotic controllers to incorporate biomimetic circuits converges toward the generation of embodied DBTs. Beyond this, the computational capacity of HPC systems also poses limits, as it is neither efficient nor fast enough to cope with real-time extended simulations. Paradoxically, to effectively simulate the brain, a neuromorphic computer based on the architecture and rules of the brain might be needed to emulate the brain (Bogdan et al., 2021; Gandolfi et al., 2022)! Finally, a key question, beyond the theoretical implementation of more accurate BDTs, is what kind of data is needed to resolve all parameters, with a single subject precision in mind, or whether current data from MRI and EEG/MEG is of sufficient quality to allow the extraction of refined region-specific physiologically meaningful parameters at single subject level. Therefore, to move BDTs toward a mechanistic physiological interpretation, future developments will require advancements on several fronts, including physiology, physics, informatics, AI, and ultimately ethics to control the outcomes of what might become the door for advanced brain-like machines applicable in medicine and technology.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Figure 1

Virtual brain models and brain digital twins. The process of brain twin generation and simulation involves several steps. (1) Neural masses provide a generic representation of the interaction between excitatory and inhibitory neurons in a local circuit taking inspiration from the cerebral cortical column (D'Angelo & Jirsa, 2022; Spiegler & Jirsa, 2013). (2) Neural masses are placed in the nodes of the virtual brain. (3) High-field MRI scans are used to extract the brain data needed to construct the virtual brain, i.e., (4) the tractographic connectome and (5) the resting-state fMRI (Palesi et al., 2020). Finally, (6) the twin is simulated to optimize its internal parameters (7) against experimental fMRI recordings.

Figure 2

VBM parameters explain brain physiopathology. Brain digital twins have been used to model the brain of patients of the dementia spectrum. The pattern of parameter changes differs considerably from Alzheimer disease (AD) to Fronto-temporal dementia (FTD) patients, revealing DMN hyperconnectivity in both categories but selective prefrontal disinhibition only in FTD (Monteverdi et al., 2022, 2023). In a study on MCI patients, virtual brain parameters have been correlated with neuropsychological scores taken from the same patients. There is a strong ($R^2>0.7$) and significant ($p<0.01$) correlation between circuit parameters and cognitive performance in multiple domains (in the example, verbal working memory is assessed against TVB parameters in the DMN, which is core to learning and memory processing). These results are consistent with clinical and neurobiological knowledge about these pathologies and support the reliability of digital twin predictions about brain functioning (Monteverdi et al., 2025).

Figure 3

Circuit-specific mean-field models. The homogeneity of nodes imposed by standard neural mass models can be surpassed by mean-field models specific to different types of neural circuits. Physiological recordings of cellular and microcircuit activity are more commonly performed in rodents, but recently, data have become available also from surgical human tissue (Masoli et al., 2024). The example shown in the figure is taken from studies on the cerebellar network. Detailed neuron models of granule cells (red), Golgi cells (blue), Purkinje cells (green), stellate cells (yellow) and basket cells (orange) were reconstructed from confocal images and patch-clamp recordings (Masoli et al., 2017, 2025; Masoli, Ottaviani, et al., 2020; Masoli, Tognolina, et al., 2020; Rizza et al., 2021). These models are then duplicated and combined to generate large modules of the cerebellar network including 10^4 - 10^5 neurons (De Schepper et al., 2022). These models can be simplified, transformed into spiking neural networks (Geminiani et al., 2023), and compressed into mean field models (Lorenzi et al., 2025), which are finally embedded into TVB nodes. This process generates ensemble signals from elementary components (D’Angelo & Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, 2017) and, mathematically, resolves a direct problem of the type $d_{obs}=F(p)$, in which d_{obs} is the observed signal and p are model parameters. The way back resolves an inverse problem of the type $p=F^{-1}(d_{obs})$, which can be solved by approximation (through an optimization process) on the mesoscale, i.e., just giving back values for free parameters in the mean field model (D’Angelo & Jirsa, 2022). Figure panels show schematics of the models with the corresponding signals underneath. In particular, a cerebellar granule cell recording is simulated with a multicompartmental model, simplified as a point neuron, and embedded into a spiking neural network (the raster plot shows the discharge of several simulated granule cells). The PSTH shows the local field potential generated by the mean field model and the corresponding BOLD signal in a simulated fMRI response.

Figure 4

Curated connectomes. The connectome extracted from MRI reconstructions is informative about the brain functional connectivity in resting-state (cf. Fig. 2). However, it is symmetrical bringing about a bidirectional and excitatory node-to-node communication. The weights are determined by tract density, and the only free parameter is the global coupling G inside a certain network or the whole brain. Beyond this, VBM evolution can leverage connectome curation. Information about the directionality of tracts and the sign of signal communication can be obtained from literature and brain atlases *a priori*. The efficiency of internode connectivity can be estimated through multiparametric optimization of the VBM. Combining this information yields the effective connectivity matrix $M^* = M^{dir} \times M^{sign} \times M^e$ which, together with intra-node parameters, represents the major output of the VBM. In this scenario, the standard VBM based on the tract density matrix, M^d , can be corrected by M^{dir} and M^{sign} and then used to initialize and normalize model parameters. Multiparametric optimization methods (e.g., (Ziaemehr et al., 2025)) on the curated connectome can then be used to extract M^e . The figure exemplifies the case of the cerebello-thalamo-cortical loop including the cerebellar cortex (CrbIcTx), deep cerebellar nuclei (DCN), thalamus (Thal), cerebral cortex (CerCtx1, CerCtx2), and anterior pontine nuclei (APN) (Palesi et al., 2020). Anatomophysiological evidence indicates that some tracts are unidirectional (APN \rightarrow CrbIcTx \rightarrow DCN \rightarrow Thal) and that some connections are inhibitory (CrbIcTx \rightarrow DCN, CerCtx \rightarrow Thal). Moreover, the weights may not be the same among network nodes (as suggested by the arbitrary weights and the false colors in M^e and M^*).

References

- Angiolelli, M., Depannemaecker, D., Agouram, H., Régis, J., Carron, R., Woodman, M., Chiodo, L., Triebkorn, P., Ziaemehr, A., Hashemi, M., Eusebio, A., Jirsa, V., & Sorrentino, P. (2025a). The Virtual Parkinsonian patient. *Npj Systems Biology and Applications*, *11*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41540-025-00516-y>
- Angiolelli, M., Depannemaecker, D., Agouram, H., Régis, J., Carron, R., Woodman, M., Chiodo, L., Triebkorn, P., Ziaemehr, A., Hashemi, M., Eusebio, A., Jirsa, V., & Sorrentino, P. (2025b). The Virtual Parkinsonian patient. *Npj Systems Biology and Applications*, *11*(1), 40. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41540-025-00516-y>
- Arbib, M. A., Erdi, P., & Szentagothai, J. (1997). *Neural Organization: Structure, Function, and Dynamics*. MIT press.
- Bogdan, P. A., Marcinnò, B., Casellato, C., Casali, S., Rowley, A. G. D., Hopkins, M., Leporati, F., D'Angelo, E., & Rhodes, O. (2021). Towards a Bio-Inspired Real-Time Neuromorphic Cerebellum. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience*, *15*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2021.622870>
- Botvinik-Nezer, R., Holzmeister, F., Camerer, C. F., Dreber, A., Huber, J., Johannesson, M., Kirchler, M., Iwanir, R., Mumford, J. A., Adcock, R. A., Avesani, P., Baczkowski, B. M., Bajracharya, A., Bakst, L., Ball, S., Barilari, M., Bault, N., Beaton, D., Beitner, J., ... Schonberg, T. (2020). Variability in the analysis of a single neuroimaging dataset by many teams. *Nature*, *582*(7810). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2314-9>
- Cayco-Gajic, N. A., Clopath, C., & Silver, R. A. (2017). Sparse synaptic connectivity is required for decorrelation and pattern separation in feedforward networks. *Nature Communications*, *8*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-01109-y>
- Cen, S., Gebregziabher, M., Moazami, S., Azevedo, C. J., & Pelletier, D. (2023). Toward precision medicine using a “digital twin” approach: modeling the onset of disease-specific brain atrophy in individuals with multiple sclerosis. *Scientific Reports*, *13*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-43618-5>
- D'Angelo, E. (2019). The cerebellum gets social. In *Science* (Vol. 363, Number 6424). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw2571>
- D'Angelo, E., Antonietti, A., Geminiani, A., Gambosi, B., Alessandro, C., Buttarazzi, E., Pedrocchi, A., & Casellato, C. (2025). Linking cellular-level phenomena to brain architecture: the case of spiking cerebellar controllers. *Neural Networks*, *188*, 107538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2025.107538>
- D'Angelo, E., & Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. (2017). Modelling the brain: Elementary components to explain ensemble functions. *Rivista Del Nuovo Cimento*, *40*(7), 297–333. <https://doi.org/10.1393/ncr/i2017-10137-5>
- D'Angelo, E., & Jirsa, V. (2022). The quest for multiscale brain modeling. In *Trends in Neurosciences* (Vol. 45, Number 10). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2022.06.007>

- De Schepper, R., Geminiani, A., Masoli, S., Rizza, M. F., Antonietti, A., Casellato, C., & D'Angelo, E. (2022). Model simulations unveil the structure-function-dynamics relationship of the cerebellar cortical microcircuit. *Communications Biology*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-04213-y>
- Deco, G., Jirsa, V. K., & McIntosh, A. R. (2011). Emerging concepts for the dynamical organization of resting-state activity in the brain. In *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* (Vol. 12, Number 1, pp. 43–56). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2961>
- Deco, G., Jirsa, V. K., & McIntosh, A. R. (2013). Resting brains never rest: Computational insights into potential cognitive architectures. In *Trends in Neurosciences* (Vol. 36, Number 5, pp. 268–274). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2013.03.001>
- Deco, G., Jirsa, V. K., Robinson, P. A., Breakspear, M., & Friston, K. (2008). The dynamic brain: From spiking neurons to neural masses and cortical fields. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 4(8), e1000092. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1000092>
- Deco, G., & Kringelbach, M. L. (2020). Turbulent-like Dynamics in the Human Brain. *Cell Reports*, 33(10). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2020.108471>
- Deco, G., Kringelbach, M. L., Arnatkeviciute, A., Oldham, S., Sabaroedin, K., Rogasch, N. C., Aquino, K. M., & Fornito, A. (2021). Dynamical consequences of regional heterogeneity in the brain's transcriptional landscape. *Science Advances*, 7(29), eabf4752. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abf4752>
- Deco, G., Kringelbach, M. L., Jirsa, V. K., & Ritter, P. (2017). The dynamics of resting fluctuations in the brain: Metastability and its dynamical cortical core. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-03073-5>
- Deco, G., Ponce-Alvarez, A., Hagmann, P., Romani, G. L., Mantini, D., & Corbetta, M. (2014). How Local Excitation-Inhibition Ratio Impacts the Whole Brain Dynamics. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 34(23), 7886–7898. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.5068-13.2014>
- Demirtaş, M., Tornador, C., Falcón, C., López-Solà, M., Hernández-Ribas, R., Pujol, J., Menchón, J. M., Ritter, P., Cardoner, N., Soriano-Mas, C., & Deco, G. (2016). Dynamic functional connectivity reveals altered variability in functional connectivity among patients with major depressive disorder. *Human Brain Mapping*, 37(8), 2918–2930. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.23215>
- Edelman, G. M., & Gally, J. A. (2001). Degeneracy and complexity in biological systems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 98(24), 13763–13768. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.231499798>
- Einevoll, G. T., Destexhe, A., Diesmann, M., Grün, S., Jirsa, V., de Kamps, M., Migliore, M., Ness, T. V., Plesser, H. E., & Schürmann, F. (2019). The Scientific Case for Brain Simulations. In *Neuron* (pp. 735–744). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2019.03.027>
- Fousek, J., Rabuffo, G., Gudibanda, K., Sheheitli, H., Jirsa, V., & Petkoski, S. (2022). *Symmetry breaking organizes the brain's resting state manifold*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.01.03.474841>
- Friston, K. J., Preller, K. H., Mathys, C., Cagnan, H., Heinzle, J., Razi, A., & Zeidman, P. (2019). Dynamic causal modelling revisited. *NeuroImage*, 199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.02.045>

- Gandolfi, D., Puglisi, F. M., Boiani, G. M., Pagnoni, G., Friston, K. J., D'Angelo, E., & Mapelli, J. (2022). Emergence of associative learning in a neuromorphic inference network. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 19(3). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ac6ca7>
- Gaviraghi, M., Lupi, E., Grosso, E., Fusari, A., Baiguera, M., Monteverdi, A., Battiston, M., Grussu, F., Kanber, B., Prados Carrasco, F., Samson, R. S., Makaronidis, J., Yiannakas, M. C., Zandi, M. S., Batterham, R. L., D'Angelo, E., Palesi, F., & Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A. M. (2025). The Sense of Smell (<sc>SoS</sc>) Atlas: Its Creation and First Application to Investigate <sc>COVID</sc> -19 Related Anosmia With a Comprehensive Quantitative <sc>MRI</sc> Protocol. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmri.70128>
- Gaviraghi, M., Monteverdi, A., Bulgheroni, S., Mercati, M., De Laurentiis, A., Nigri, A., Grisoli, M., D'Arrigo, S., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A., Casellato, C., Palesi, F., & D'Angelo, E. (2026). Brain digital twins reveal network changes in congenital and slowly progressive cerebellar ataxias. *BiorXiv*.
- Geminiani, A., Casellato, C., Boele, H.-J., Pedrocchi, A., Zeeuw, C. I. De, & D'Angelo, E. (2023). Mesoscale simulations predict the role of synergistic cerebellar plasticity during classical eyeblink conditioning. *BioRxiv*.
- Geminiani, A., Meier, J. M., Perdakis, D., Ouertani, S., Casellato, C., Ritter, P., & D'Angelo, E. U. (2026). *The Cerebellar Engine: Multiscale Digital Brain Co-simulations Reveal How Cerebellar Spiking Architecture Shapes Cortical Coherence*. <https://doi.org/10.64898/2026.04.02.715849>
- Ghosh, A., Rho, Y., McIntosh, A. R., Kötter, R., & Jirsa, V. K. (2008). Cortical network dynamics with time delays reveals functional connectivity in the resting brain. *Cognitive Neurodynamics*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11571-008-9044-2>
- Goldman, J. S., Kusch, L., Yalcinkaya, B. H., Depannemaecker, D., Nghiem, T.-A. E., Jirsa, V., & Destexhe, A. (2020). Brain-scale emergence of slow-wave synchrony and highly responsive asynchronous states based on biologically realistic population models simulated in The Virtual Brain. *BioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.12.28.424574>
- Hashemi, M., Depannemaecker, D., Saggio, M., Triebkorn, P., Rabuffo, G., Fousek, J., Ziaeemehr, A., Sip, V., Athanasiadis, A., Breyton, M., Woodman, M., Wang, H., Petkoski, S., Sorrentino, P., & Jirsa, V. (2025). Principles and Operation of Virtual Brain Twins. *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RBME.2025.3562951>
- Hashemi, M., Vattikonda, A. N., Jha, J., Sip, V., Woodman, M. M., Bartolomei, F., & Jirsa, V. K. (2023). Amortized Bayesian inference on generative dynamical network models of epilepsy using deep neural density estimators. *Neural Networks*, 163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2023.03.040>
- Hashemi, M., Vattikonda, A. N., Sip, V., Diaz-Pier, S., Peyser, A., Wang, H., Guye, M., Bartolomei, F., Woodman, M. M., & Jirsa, V. K. (2021). On the influence of prior information evaluated by fully Bayesian criteria in a personalized whole-brain model of epilepsy spread. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 17(7). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009129>
- Hashemi, M., Vattikonda, A. N., Sip, V., Guye, M., Bartolomei, F., Woodman, M. M., & Jirsa, V. K. (2020). The Bayesian Virtual Epileptic Patient: A probabilistic framework designed to infer the spatial map of

epileptogenicity in a personalized large-scale brain model of epilepsy spread. *NeuroImage*, 217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2020.116839>

Houssaini, K. El, Bernard, C., & Jirsa, V. K. (2020). The epileptor model: A systematic mathematical analysis linked to the dynamics of seizures, refractory status epilepticus, and depolarization block. *ENeuro*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0485-18.2019>

Jansen, B. H., & Rit, V. G. (1995). Electroencephalogram and visual evoked potential generation in a mathematical model of coupled cortical columns. *Biological Cybernetics*, 73(4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00199471>

Jirsa, V. K., & Haken, H. (1996). Field theory of electromagnetic brain activity. *Physical Review Letters*, 77(5). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.77.960>

Jirsa, V. K., & Haken, H. (1997). A derivation of a macroscopic field theory of the brain from the quasi-microscopic neural dynamics. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, 99(4). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2789\(96\)00166-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2789(96)00166-2)

Jirsa, V. K., Jantzen, K. J., Fuchs, A., & Kelso, J. A. S. (2002). Spatiotemporal forward solution of the EEG and MEG using network modeling. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, 21(5). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2002.1009385>

Jirsa, V. K., Sporns, O., Breakspear, M., Deco, G., & McIntosh, A. R. (2010). Towards the virtual brain: Network modeling of the intact and the damaged brain. *Archives Italiennes de Biologie*, 148(3), 189–205. <https://doi.org/10.4449/aib.v148i3.1223>

Jirsa, V., Wang, H., Triebkorn, P., Hashemi, M., Jha, J., Gonzalez-Martinez, J., Guye, M., Makhalova, J., & Bartolomei, F. (2023). Personalised virtual brain models in epilepsy. In *The Lancet Neurology* (Vol. 22, Number 5). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(23\)00008-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(23)00008-X)

Koch, Christof. (2004). *The quest for consciousness : a neurobiological approach*. Roberts and Co.

Li, G., Hsu, L.-M., Wu, Y., Bozoki, A. C., Shih, Y.-Y. I., & Yap, P.-T. (2025). Revealing excitation-inhibition imbalance in Alzheimer's disease using multiscale neural model inversion of resting-state functional MRI. *Communications Medicine*, 5(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43856-025-00736-7>

Llinás, R. . (2002). *I of the vortex : from neurons to self*. MIT.

Lorenzi, R. M., Geminiani, A., Zerlaut, Y., De Grazia, M., Destexhe, A., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A. M., Palesi, F., Casellato, C., & D'Angelo, E. (2023). A multi-layer mean-field model of the cerebellum embedding microstructure and population-specific dynamics. *PLOS Computational Biology*, 19(9), e1011434. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1011434>

Lorenzi, R. M., Palesi, F., Casellato, C., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A. M., & D'Angelo, E. (2025). Region-specific mean field models enhance simulations of local and global brain dynamics. *Npj Systems Biology and Applications*, 11(1), 66. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41540-025-00543-9>

Mainzer, Klaus. (2013). *Symmetries of Nature : a Handbook for Philosophy of Nature and Science*. De Gruyter.

- Martin, H. M., Cofre, R., & Destexhe, A. (2025). *Simulated 5-HT_{2A} receptor activation accounts for the high complexity of brain activity during psychedelic states*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.10.20.683366>
- Masoli, S., Ottaviani, A., Casali, S., & D'Angelo, E. (2020). Cerebellar Golgi cell models predict dendritic processing and mechanisms of synaptic plasticity. *PLoS Computational Biology*, *16*(12 December). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007937>
- Masoli, S., Rizza, M. F., Sgritta, M., Van Geit, W., Schürmann, F., & D'Angelo, E. (2017). Single neuron optimization as a basis for accurate biophysical modeling: The case of cerebellar granule cells. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience*, *11*, 71. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2017.00071>
- Masoli, S., Rizza, M. F., Soda, T., Sánchez-Ponce, D., Munoz, A., Prestori, F., & D'Angelo, E. (2025). Cerebellar basket cell filtering of Purkinje cell responses elicited by low frequency parallel fibre transmission. *Scientific Reports*, *15*(1), 25192. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-09964-2>
- Masoli, S., Sanchez-Ponce, D., Vrieler, N., Abu-Haya, K., Lerner, V., Shahar, T., Nedelescu, H., Rizza, M. F., Benavides-Piccione, R., DeFelipe, J., Yarom, Y., Munoz, A., & D'Angelo, E. (2024). Human Purkinje cells outperform mouse Purkinje cells in dendritic complexity and computational capacity. *Communications Biology*, *7*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-05689-y>
- Masoli, S., Tognolina, M., Laforenza, U., Moccia, F., & D'Angelo, E. (2020). Parameter tuning differentiates granule cell subtypes enriching transmission properties at the cerebellum input stage. *Communications Biology*, *3*(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-020-0953-x>
- Mazzara, C., Ziaemehr, A., Troisi Lopez, E., Cipriano, L., Angiolelli, M., Sparaco, M., Quarantelli, M., Granata, C., Sorrentino, G., Hashemi, M., Jirsa, V., & Sorrentino, P. (2025). Mapping Brain Lesions to Conduction Delays: The Next Step for Personalized Brain Models in Multiple Sclerosis. *Human Brain Mapping*, *46*(7). <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.70219>
- Meier, J. M., Perdakis, D., Blickensdörfer, A., Stefanovski, L., Liu, Q., Maith, O., Dinkelbach, H., Baladron, J., Hamker, F. H., & Ritter, P. (2022). Virtual deep brain stimulation: Multiscale co-simulation of a spiking basal ganglia model and a whole-brain mean-field model with The Virtual Brain. *Experimental Neurology*, *354*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.expneurol.2022.114111>
- Melozzi, F., Woodman, M. M., Jirsa, V. K., & Bernard, C. (2017). The virtual mouse brain: A computational neuroinformatics platform to study whole mouse brain dynamics. *ENeuro*, *4*(3), ENEURO.0111-17.2017. <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0111-17.2017>
- Missey, F., Acerbo, E., Dickey, A. S., Trajlinek, J., Studnička, O., Lubrano, C., de Araújo e Silva, M., Brady, E., Všíanský, V., Szabo, J., Dolezalova, I., Fabo, D., Pail, M., Gutekunst, C. A., Migliore, R., Migliore, M., Lagarde, S., Carron, R., Karimi, F., ... Williamson, A. (2026). Non-invasive temporal interference stimulation of the hippocampus suppresses epileptic biomarkers in patients with Epilepsy: biophysical differences between kilohertz and amplitude modulated stimulation. *Brain Stimulation*, *19*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brs.2025.11.008>
- Monteverdi, A., Cotta Ramusino, M., Conca, F., Augello, A., Totaro, C., Grasso, P., Castelnovo, A., Lorenzi, R., Terzaghi, M., Farina, L., Costa, A., Pichiecchio, A., Cappa, S., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C., Palesi, F., & D'Angelo, E. (2026). Virtual brain and electroencephalography explain the variance of memory alterations in mild cognitive impairment. *BiorXiv*.

- Monteverdi, A., Cotta Ramusino, M., Conca, F., Manzon, S., Redolfi, A., Lupi, E., De Grazia, M., Lorenzi, R. M., Gaviraghi, M., Mazzocchi, L., Farina, L. M., Costa, A., Pichiecchio, A., Cappa, S., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A. M., Palesi, F., & D'Angelo, E. U. (2025). *Alterations in Topological and Dynamical Parameters Correlate with Disease Biomarkers and Neuropsychological Scores in Prodromic Stages of Dementia*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5227250>
- Monteverdi, A., Palesi, F., Costa, A., Vitali, P., Pichiecchio, A., Cotta Ramusino, M., Bernini, S., Jirsa, V., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A. M., & D'Angelo, E. (2022). Subject-specific features of excitation/inhibition profiles in neurodegenerative diseases. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience, 14*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2022.868342>
- Monteverdi, A., Palesi, F., Schirner, M., Argentino, F., Merante, M., Redolfi, A., Conca, F., Mazzocchi, L., Cappa, S. F., Cotta Ramusino, M., Costa, A., Pichiecchio, A., Farina, L. M., Jirsa, V., Ritter, P., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A. M., & D'Angelo, E. (2023). Virtual brain simulations reveal network-specific parameters in neurodegenerative dementias. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience, 15*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2023.1204134>
- Palesi, F., Lorenzi, R. M., Casellato, C., Ritter, P., Jirsa, V., Gandini Wheeler-Kingshott, C. A. M., & D'Angelo, E. (2020). The Importance of Cerebellar Connectivity on Simulated Brain Dynamics. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience, 14*, 240. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2020.00240>
- Petkoski, S., & Jirsa, V. K. (2019). Transmission time delays organize the brain network synchronization. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences, 377*(2153). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2018.0132>
- Petkoski, S., & Jirsa, V. K. (2022). Normalizing the brain connectome for communication through synchronization. *Network Neuroscience, 6*(3). https://doi.org/10.1162/netn_a_00231
- Rizza, M. F., Locatelli, F., Masoli, S., Sánchez-Ponce, D., Muñoz, A., Prestori, F., & D'Angelo, E. (2021). Stellate cell computational modeling predicts signal filtering in the molecular layer circuit of cerebellum. *Scientific Reports, 11*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-83209-w>
- Roy, D., & Jirsa, V. (2013). Inferring network properties of cortical neurons with synaptic coupling and parameter dispersion. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2013.00020>
- Sacha, M., Tesler, F., Cofre, R., & Destexhe, A. (2025). A computational approach to evaluate how molecular mechanisms impact large-scale brain activity. *Nature Computational Science, 5*(5), 405–417. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-025-00796-8>
- Schirner, M., Deco, G., & Ritter, P. (2023). Learning how network structure shapes decision-making for bio-inspired computing. *Nature Communications, 14*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-38626-y>
- Schirner, M., McIntosh, A. R., Jirsa, V., Deco, G., & Ritter, P. (2018). Inferring multi-scale neural mechanisms with brain network modelling. *ELife, 7*, e28927. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.28927>
- Singer, W. (2009). The brain, a complex self-organizing system. *European Review, 17*(2). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1062798709000751>

- Sorrentino, P., Pathak, A., Ziaemehr, A., Troisi Lopez, E., Cipriano, L., Romano, A., Sparaco, M., Quarantelli, M., Banerjee, A., Sorrentino, G., Jirsa, V., & Hashemi, M. (2024). The virtual multiple sclerosis patient. *iScience*, 27(7). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.110101>
- Spiegler, A., & Jirsa, V. (2013). Systematic approximations of neural fields through networks of neural masses in the virtual brain. *NeuroImage*, 83, 704–725. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2013.06.018>
- Stefanovski, L., Triebkorn, P., Spiegler, A., Diaz-Cortes, M. A., Solodkin, A., Jirsa, V., McIntosh, A. R., & Ritter, P. (2019). Linking Molecular Pathways and Large-Scale Computational Modeling to Assess Candidate Disease Mechanisms and Pharmacodynamics in Alzheimer’s Disease. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2019.00054>
- Tartarini, L., Triebkorn, P., Kusch, L., Solinas, S., Wang, H., Gandolfi, D., Jirsa, V., & Mapelli, J. (2026). Co-simulation framework combining a microscopically detailed point neuron model of the hippocampal CA1 region with the macroscopic high-resolution virtual brain model. *Journal of Computational Neuroscience*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10827-026-00925-w>
- Tesler, F., Lorenzi, R. M., Ponzi, A., Casellato, C., Palesi, F., Gandolfi, D., Gandini Wheeler Kingshott, C. A. M., Mapelli, J., D’Angelo, E., Migliore, M., & Destexhe, A. (2024). Multiscale modeling of neuronal dynamics in hippocampus CA1. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2024.1432593>
- Thivierge, J. P., & Marcus, G. F. (2007). The topographic brain: from neural connectivity to cognition. *Trends in Neurosciences*, 30(6). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2007.04.004>
- Tononi, G., Sporns, O., & Edelman, G. M. (1999). Measures of degeneracy and redundancy in biological networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 96(6), 3257–3262. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.96.6.3257>
- Triebkorn, P., Stefanovski, L., Dhindsa, K., Diaz-Cortes, M. A., Bey, P., Bülau, K., Pai, R., Spiegler, A., Solodkin, A., Jirsa, V., McIntosh, A. R., & Ritter, P. (2022). Brain simulation augments machine-learning–based classification of dementia. *Alzheimer’s and Dementia: Translational Research and Clinical Interventions*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/trc2.12303>
- Wang, H. E., Dollomaja, B., Triebkorn, P., Duma, G. M., Williamson, A., Makhalova, J., Lemarechal, J. D., Bartolomei, F., & Jirsa, V. (2025). Virtual brain twins for stimulation in epilepsy. *Nature Computational Science*, 5(9). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-025-00841-6>
- Wang, H. E., Triebkorn, P., Breyton, M., Dollomaja, B., Lemarechal, J. D., Petkoski, S., Sorrentino, P., Depannemaecker, D., Hashemi, M., & Jirsa, V. K. (2024). Virtual brain twins: From basic neuroscience to clinical use. In *National Science Review* (Vol. 11, Number 5). <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwae079>
- Wong, K. F., & Wang, X. J. (2006). A recurrent network mechanism of time integration in perceptual decisions. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 26(4). <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3733-05.2006>
- Zeidman, P., Friston, K., & Parr, T. (2023). A primer on Variational Laplace (VL). *NeuroImage*, 279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2023.120310>

- Zerlaut, Y., Chemla, S., Chavane, F., & Destexhe, A. (2018). Modeling mesoscopic cortical dynamics using a mean-field model of conductance-based networks of adaptive exponential integrate-and-fire neurons. *Journal of Computational Neuroscience*, *44*(1), 45–61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10827-017-0668-2>
- Zerlaut, Y., Chemla, S., Chavane, F., & Destexhe*, A. (2017). Modeling mesoscopic cortical dynamics using a mean-field model of conductance-based networks of adaptive exponential integrate-and-fire neurons. *Journal of Computational Neuroscience*, *44*(1), 45–61. <https://doi.org/10.1101/168385>
- Ziaemehr, A., Woodman, M., Domide, L., Petkoski, S., Jirsa, V., & Hashemi, M. (2025). *Virtual Brain Inference (VBI): A flexible and integrative toolkit for efficient probabilistic inference on virtual brain models*. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.106194.3>
- Zimmermann, J., Perry, A., Breakspear, M., Schirner, M., Sachdev, P., Wen, W., Kochan, N. A., Mapstone, M., Ritter, P., McIntosh, A. R., & Solodkin, A. (2018). Differentiation of Alzheimer’s disease based on local and global parameters in personalized Virtual Brain models. *NeuroImage: Clinical*, *19*, 240–251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2018.04.017>